

Quick Guide to

Research Infrastructures

for Humanities Scholars

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What is a Research Infrastructure?

Research infrastructures (RIs) provide resources and services for different research communities. These include (but are not limited to): major equipment or sets of instruments, knowledge-related facilities such as collections, archives or scientific data infrastructures, computing systems and communication networks.

RIs play a crucial role in supporting humanities and heritage researchers by providing access to data, tools, and services. But more than that - they exist as permanent international entities that bring together and represent communities of various disciplines. They provide coordinated and centralised services and offer a forum for exchange of knowledge and experience between the scholars and practitioners, beyond national boundaries. They also offer the important service of relieving smaller institutions of the burdens of having to establish complex technical systems which is essential to being able to share their collections online.

Paul Otlet, *Traité de documentation*, 1934
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Are Research Infrastructures for me?

As humanities and heritage researchers, whose work does not necessarily produce the same large amounts of data as, for example, research in the natural or life sciences does, you may be wondering: What's this got to do with me? Well, we hope that this Quick Guide addresses that question by clarifying the benefits of engaging with European RIs, whether you are looking to access existing datasets or deposit your own, (and we'll show how the difference between these interactions matters).

In this guide we chose to explicitly include those infrastructures that align with the principles of openness, fairness, and non-commercial use. We also distinguish between distributed and national infrastructures, to help you navigate how to interact with them. Though primarily designed for researchers within Europe, we recognize that scholars worldwide seek access to these infrastructures, whether for depositing materials or retrieving data. Rather than listing individual projects, we emphasize registries, aggregators, and overviews that provide sustainable, long-term access to the wealth of resources available.

Quick Guide

to EU Research Infrastructures for Humanities Scholars

Humanities research increasingly relies on digital infrastructures and resources for accessing, analysing, and disseminating digital objects and data. This guide introduces key European research infrastructures and resources designed to support individual humanities scholars in data access, tool and workflow selection, training, and publishing.

For whom?

- Researchers working with Europe's cultural heritage
- Scholars interested in open, non-profit, and fair infrastructures
- Researchers accessing data & tools from outside Europe

This guide includes resources that are:

- Open
 - ↳ International (with a European emphasis)
 - ↳ Directories, aggregators and overviews
 - ↳ Cultural heritage-related

Many of these resources are funded by the European Union, supporting research through non-profit and collaborative frameworks.

These icons help you spot the resources you need:

Access digital heritage
objects & data

Publish output & data

Get research tools
& workflows

EU-funded

Learn through tutorials
and training resources

Archives Portal Europe

[Read more](#)

An archive aggregator, linking metadata from a large variety national, community, university, and private archives across Europe.

- Finding aids and (links to) digitised documents
- Institutional metadata (opening times, holdings, contacts)

CLARIN Virtual Language Observatory

[Read more](#)

A web portal for linguistic resources, providing access to language datasets, tools, and services.

- Searchable linguistic corpora and tools
- CLARIN is an infrastructure supporting research based on language resources

DARIAH-Campus

[Read more](#)

A learning platform offering how-to guides, courses, and tutorials for digitally-enabled arts and humanities.

- With a Digital Humanities Course Registry
- DARIAH is a pan-European infrastructure for arts and humanities scholars

Europeana.eu

[Read more](#)

A portal aggregating over 60 million digitised cultural heritage artifacts from 3,000+ institutions across Europe.

- Aggregated metadata and (links to) European digital heritage objects
- Also APIs for data access

Europeana Academy

[Read more](#)

A training programme to build capacity in professionals working with, in and around cultural heritage.

- Live, instructor-led training sessions
- Self-paced courses

COMMON EUROPEAN
DATA SPACE FOR
CULTURAL HERITAGE

Hypotheses

[Read more](#)

An online platform for academic blogs in the humanities and social sciences.

- In English, French, German, and Spanish
- Part of the OpenEdition Center, a French public research body

 Hypotheses

EUscreen

[Read more](#)

A digital archive of European audiovisual media, including historical TV programs from 1900 to today.

- Aggregated metadata and video clips
- Connected to Europeana.eu

OAPEN Open Access Books Toolkit

[Read more](#)

A toolkit to help academic authors publish in open access.

- Articles on many aspects of open access book publishing

 **BOOKS
TOOLKIT**

OpenMethods

[Read more](#)

A community-driven platform, highlighting digital humanities methods, tools, and reflections.

- Curated and aggregated by experts

OPENMETHODS

Openverse

Read more

An open-source search engine for openly licensed images and audio tracks.

- By Creative Commons
- Also available via API

re3data

Read more

A comprehensive global directory of research data repositories, covering all academic disciplines.

- Searchable registry of research data repositories

Programming Historian

A peer-reviewed tutorial platform for learning digital humanities tools, techniques, and workflows.

- In English, French, and Portuguese

Read more

The Rogue Scholar

Read more

A platform that archives, indexes, and enhances academic/science blogs.

- Register your academic blog
- Assigns DOIs, permanent identifiers for your blog posts

 The Rogue Scholar

Navigating the European Research Infrastructure Landscape

This Quick Guide focuses on research tools, services, and infrastructures that we think are the most useful for individual humanities researchers. But not all of them are, strictly speaking, infrastructures, and some of them are only parts of larger ones.

To help you navigate this landscape, this section provides a high-level overview of key European humanities research infrastructures and related initiatives. Some are long-term infrastructures, while others are time-limited projects that contribute to or build on them. The entries below follow a loose logic: from policy and funding, through legal and organisational frameworks, to concrete infrastructures and initiatives.

At the strategic level, [ESFRI](#) (the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures) supports a coordinated, strategy-led approach to research infrastructure policy in Europe. Its delegates, nominated by national research ministries, work alongside the European Commission to shape long-term priorities.

Funding largely flows through [Horizon Europe](#), the EU's main research and innovation programme (and successor to Horizon 2020), overseen by [DG Research and Innovation](#). Many infrastructure-related projects originate here. For example, [SSHOC](#), the Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud project, which helped develop the social sciences and humanities component of the European Open Science Cloud.

Policy and funding are closely linked to implementation. [DG CONNECT](#), the European Commission's Directorate-General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology, plays a central role in investing in and coordinating digital research infrastructures. It manages or co-manages key programmes such as the [Digital Europe Programme](#) (supporting

supercomputing, AI, data spaces, and digital innovation hubs) as well as parts of Horizon Europe.

At the legal and organisational level, two key EU frameworks structure how infrastructures are set up: ERICs and EDICs.

An [ERIC](#) (European Research Infrastructure Consortium) is a legal entity designed specifically to establish and operate research infrastructures of European interest on a non-economic basis. There are now over 30 ERICs, including [DARIAH](#) (arts and humanities), [CLARIN](#) (language resources), [EHRI](#) (Holocaust research), and [E-RIHS](#) (heritage science).

An [EDIC](#) (European Digital Infrastructure Consortium) is a newer framework designed for large-scale digital infrastructures that extend beyond research. EDICs bring together Member States and other stakeholders to build shared infrastructure and services. For example, [ALT-EDIC](#) addresses the shortage of European language data for AI training.

Alongside these frameworks, broader ecosystem concepts have emerged, such as data spaces and clouds, adding, inevitably, another layer of complexity. Data spaces and clouds are complementary pillars of Europe's digital strategy for sovereignty (in other words, ensuring that data holders

remain in control of their data), but they serve different purposes.

[Common European Data Spaces](#) are decentralised frameworks for sharing data securely across organisations and sectors. They are defined by shared governance models, usage policies, and semantic interoperability. In the cultural heritage domain, the [Europeana](#) Initiative stewards the [Common European data space for cultural heritage](#).

Cloud infrastructures, on the other hand, provide the technical environment for storage and computing. One of the central initiatives is [EOSC](#) (the European Open Science Cloud), which aims to create a federated system of interoperable research services and data across disciplines and countries, less a single cloud, more a 'cloud of clouds.'

Meanwhile, [ECHOES](#), a consortium of 51 partners, is laying the groundwork for the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage (ECCCH), a European Commission initiative to create a shared digital environment for heritage professionals and researchers, offering access to data, tools, and training resources.

SSH Open Marketplace

[Read more](#)

A curated repository of tools, datasets, training materials, and workflows for Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) researchers.

- Searchable datasets, software, and workflows
- Entry point to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)

VERA

[Read more](#)

An online platform to do participatory Humanities and Social Sciences research.

- Facilitating collaboration
- Building a Citizen Science project

Wikidata

[Read more](#)

A free, collaborative, structured knowledge base that stores facts about people, places, things, and concepts so they can be shared and reused online.

- Access structured data for research
- Aggregate your data with others

Think. Check. Submit.

A toolkit to help researchers identify trusted journals and publishers.

- Tools and practical resources

[Read more](#)

Wikimedia Commons

Read more

A free, collaborative media repository, containing images, audio, video, and more, that anyone can use.

- Find free to use multimedia
- Share media for wider reuse

Do you have a suggestion to improve this Quick Guide?

Feel free to contact us at research@europeana.eu

Notes:

Zenodo

Read more

A general-purpose open repository for publishing research papers, presentations, poster, datasets, and software.

- Assigns DOIs, permanent identifiers for digital resources
- Supports both open and restricted access

zenodo

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